

Conceptual Design of a Compliant, Low-Cost Prosthetic Hand

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Abstract—This paper addresses the conceptual design and the virtual prototyping of a low-cost, under-actuated prosthetic hand. Particular attention has been paid to ensuring that size, weight, and appearance are as similar as possible to those of a human hand, in order to increase user acceptance. The proposed device comprises a total of 10 Degrees of Freedom (DoF) and 4 Degrees of Actuation (DoA), three of which are enabled by employing electric motors and a tendon transmission system, whereas the last DoA is simply manually actuated by the end-user (e.g. using the still-functioning limb). The virtual prototype of the hand allows easy evaluation of the hand’s grasping capabilities as well as its maximum gripping force.

Index Terms—Virtual Prototyping, Hand Design, Elastic Hinges, Soft Finger, Tendon Actuation

I. INTRODUCTION

Recognizing and understanding the complexity of the human hand to replicate it in a robotic prosthesis is a challenge faced by many researchers. In fact, the loss of an upper limb makes it difficult to even carry out the simplest activities of daily living, such as cleaning and cooking. Robotic hands can be of great help in performing these activities, although, as reported in [1], despite decades of research and development, current prosthetic solutions are still too limited and consequently poorly accepted by the user, mainly because of low anthropomorphism, difficulty of use, and lack of sensory feedback. Another obstacle to the diffusion of prosthetic hands is their average price, which is still too high to be affordable for everyone. This paper presents the design of a novel, low-cost, under-actuated anthropomorphic hand that can be fabricated almost entirely using rapid prototyping technology. The presented hand provides a good starting point for future developments, which should primarily focus on the implementation of tactile sensors and related electronics.

A. Hand Design

The robotic hands currently presented in the literature mainly follow two different design approaches: a) hands that attempt to accurately mimic the capabilities of human limbs

via complex mechanical systems and a large number of actuators and sensors [2], which are mostly used in collaborative industrial robots due to their size, or b) anthropomorphic, under-actuated hands suitable for use in prosthetic devices [3], [4]. In developing the robotic hand presented in this abstract, the primary goal has been to design a hand that is as similar as possible to its human counterpart, while trying to reduce the cost by employing additive manufacturing along with generic mass-produced motors and mechanical components. Referring to the study conducted by NASA in 2000 [5], it has been decided to design a hand whose dimensions correspond to the average between the 50th percentile of men and women (i.e., 18.25 cm long and 8.35 cm wide). As shown in Table I and Figure 1, the presented hand comprises 10 DoF, 9 of which are tendon-actuated and realized with spring-based compliant elements directly mimicking those employed in the UB hand III [2] (i.e. all proximal and distal joints of the fingers), whereas the last one (i.e. the thumb abduction joint) is designed to be mechanically actuated with 3 different locking positions using a spring plunger. The thumb abduction allows the hand to transition from the power grasp configuration to the pinch grasp configuration and to the lateral grasp configuration. By using three *Maxon A-max 16 DC motors*, it is possible to

TABLE I: Hand’s Datasheet.

DoF		
Joint	Symbol	Value
Thumb Abduction	T_{ABD}	$[-30,0,+30]^\circ$
Proximal flexion	T_P, I_P, M_P, R_P, L_P	$[0,90]^\circ$
Distal flexion	I_D, M_D, R_D, L_D	$[0,90]^\circ$
Design Parameters		
Hand size (Length x width)	18.25 x 8.35 [cm]	
Hand weight	308 [g]	
Hand max gripping force	37 [N]	
Compliant joints stiffness	30 [Nmm ²]	
Compression springs constant	1.46 [N/mm]	
Springs material	spring steel	
Motor diameter	16 [mm]	
Motor length	48 [mm]	
Motor torque	200 [Nmm]	

Fig. 1: Design of the proposed hand.

individually actuate the thumb and index finger, which are connected to the first and second motors, respectively, whereas the other three fingers are connected to the third motor via a linear slide with three compression springs. The springs are used to decouple the motor from the fingers so that they can perfectly adapt to the object to be grasped and complete their flexion, even if one of the fingers cannot flex further. In fact, in the latter case, the corresponding spring begins to compress without completely preventing the downward movement of the linear guide and thus the rotation of the motor. Finally, it is important to note that the fingertips are hollow to allow for a better grip when made of a flexible material (e.g., TPU). The rest of the hand has been designed to be made with a 3D printer from ABS.

II. VIRTUAL PROTOTYPING

To roughly evaluate hand gripping capabilities, a virtual prototype has been realized and tested in a Multi-Body environment (Recurdyn), the compliant joints being simply simulated employing torsional springs elements whose stiffness k can be expressed as follows [6]:

$$k = 0.95 (Er^5)/[RL(2 + \nu)]$$

where $R = D/2$ is the outer spring radius, $r = d/2$ is the wire radius, L is the coil length, E and ν are the Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of the material, respectively. Figure 2 shows how the virtual prototype grips different objects with its three possible thumb configurations. The following results have been obtained for the maximum gripping forces: a) 9 N for the pinch grasp, b) 25 N for the cylindrical grasp, c) 37 N for the power grasp, and d) 8 N for the lateral grasp.

III. CONCLUSIONS

In this long abstract, a low-cost, under-actuated prosthetic hand has been presented and virtually tested in a Recurdyn flexible Multi-Body environment. The proposed hand achieves

Fig. 2: Grasp simulations.

a maximum gripping force of 37 N at a total cost of about 370 Euros, which is about half the force at a fraction of the price compared to other hands already on the market. Future plans include extensive testing of the physical hand prototype (currently in production) to measure its gripping capabilities in a real-world scenario, as well as the integration of tactile sensors in the fingertips.

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